

TOMORROW'S ROADMAP: INNOVATIONS IN THERMAL MANAGEMENT FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLES

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Introduction: Electric vehicles (EVs) offer a potential solution to face the global energy crisis and climate change issues in the transportation sector. Currently, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries have gained popularity as a source of energy in EVs, owing to several benefits including higher power density. To compete with internal combustion (IC) engine vehicles, the capacity of Li-ion batteries is continuously increasing to improve the efficiency and reliability of EVs. The performance characteristics and safe operations of Li-ion batteries depend on their operating temperature which demands the effective thermal management of Li-ion batteries. The commercially employed cooling strategies have several obstructions to enable the desired thermal management of high-power density batteries with allowable maximum temperature and symmetrical temperature distribution. The efforts are striving in the direction of searching for advanced cooling strategies which could eliminate the limitations of current cooling strategies and be employed in next-generation battery thermal management systems. The present review summarizes numerous research studies that explore advanced cooling strategies for battery thermal management in EVs [1].

Main Part: In this article we only discuss *Battery electric vehicles* (BEVs) are powered entirely by electric motor and use rechargeable batteries for the energy storage. The main components of the electric drive system include battery pack, gearbox, inverter, and induction motor. Batteries can be charged externally by connecting BEVs to grid electricity. Additionally, the regenerative braking mechanism converts mechanical energy into electric charge, which is also supplied to the battery [2].

Picture 1: Battery Electric Vehicles

Batteries are an important part of EVs, regardless of their type. The lack of reliable, small, and

lightweight batteries has long been an issue, but *lithium-ion batteries* (LIBs) offer both economic and technological solutions to the problem. LIBs offer a less toxic and higher-energy storage potential than lead-acid batteries do, and they can be designed with various chemical combinations. Each battery cell in LIBs consists of four components: cathode, anode, electrolyte, and separator. The characteristics of the battery cell vary depending on the cathode's chemical composition. The common cathode chemistries used in EV batteries include: lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide (NMC), lithium nickel cobalt aluminum oxide (NCA), and lithium iron phosphate (LFP) [3].

Recent developments, especially relating to electric cars, show an optimistic trend for the EV industry. With major car manufacturers joining the race, a rapid growth in production and sales of electric cars is expected in the coming years [4]. The growth of EVs is expected to follow the

S-curve trend, which is a typical pattern for new technology adoption.¹⁴ Like other technological advancements, it can be inferred that battery technology will evolve rapidly, and as the price of EV batteries continues to decrease, the adoption of EVs will grow substantially. Besides financial and technological factors, the growth will also depend on transport and energy policies, as well as consumer preferences and infrastructure for supporting the rapid adoption of EVs. The role of private sector players, including vehicle manufacturers and charging infrastructure operators, will also be equally important in the expansion of electric mobility [5]. Despite numerous benefits and an optimistic growth outlook, EVs face some crucial challenges. Higher purchase price, lack of supportive infrastructure and clean energy, and the need for a sustainable supply of material resources are some of the key challenges that need addressing in order for EVs to become a steadfast replacement for ICEVs.

Numerous reviews have been reported in recent years on battery thermal management based on various cooling strategies, primarily focusing on air cooling and indirect liquid cooling. Owing to the limitations of these conventional cooling strategies the research has been diverted to advanced cooling strategies for battery thermal management. Considerable research has been reported on phase change material cooling and direct liquid cooling as a replacement for conventional air and indirect liquid cooling for battery thermal management. There are review articles reported recently that solely focus on phase change material cooling as an advanced battery thermal management technique. However, the open literature is lacking to present a comprehensive review that solely focuses on direct liquid cooling for next-generation battery thermal management. It should be noted that there are reviews that

explain the research studies on direct liquid cooling for battery thermal management but only as a subpart of the entire review [6].

Conclusion: Phase change material cooling and direct liquid cooling are elaborated as advanced cooling strategies for battery thermal management systems in the present review. In phase change material cooling, the battery is surrounded by materials that absorb the heat generated by the battery during charging/discharging operations. This material changes its phase owing to the heat absorbed from the battery and thus maintains the optimum temperature of the battery.

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